

A facile microwave-induced synthesis of heterocyclic compounds and a dialdehyde from a naturally occurring limonoid

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Abstract : Paniculatin (**1**) (6 α -acetoxyazadirone), a naturally occurring meliacin, was subjected to chemical transformations under microwave irradiation to give heterocyclic compounds and also a dialdehyde derivative. These include 2-methyloxazolo[4,5-*d*]-1,2,20,21,22,23-hexahydropaniculatin (**4**), 2-methyloxazolo[4,5-*d*]-6 α ,7 α -dihydroxy-1,2,20,21,22,23-hexahydropaniculatin (**5**) and the dialdehyde (**9**) derivative of paniculatin. These reactions give excellent yields in a very short time when carried out under microwave irradiation under solvent-free condition.

Keywords : Microwave, Meliaceae, limonoids, paniculatin, heterocycles.

Introduction

Microwave irradiation can be used to carry out a wide range of reactions in a solvent free manner in short times and with high conversions and selectivity¹. This approach is beneficial since the recovery of solvents from conventional reaction systems always results in some losses.

*Chisocheton paniculatus*² Hiern (family : Meliaceae) occurs as a tree in the forests of Assam, the fruit of which is capsule, 1.5–3 inches across, globose with pyriform base. It has been reported that a number of species of this family exhibit physiological activity³. In our continuing studies^{4,5} on the Meliaceae of the NER of India, we have investigated the fruits of *Chisocheton paniculatus*, collected from the tropical evergreen forest of Nambor Reserved Forest of Golaghat district of Assam, India.

Limonoids have attracted much attention because of the marked insect antifeedant and growth-regulating, antifungal activity of azadirachtin and related limonoids isolated from the neem tree and also of few limonoids isolated from the fruits of *Chisocheton paniculatus* Hiern⁵⁻⁷. More recently limonoids have shown anticarcinogenic and antitumorigenic activities⁷. A pure compound paniculatin⁸ (**1**) (6 α -acetoxyazadirone) was isolated from the fruit of *Chisocheton paniculatus*⁴.

Mild alkaline hydrolysis of **1** with methanolic KOH

gave the corresponding diol (**6**), C₂₈H₃₄O₄, m.p. 181.1 °C. The two CHOAc protons appearing at δ 5.42 and 5.47 in **1** appeared as a multiplet centered at δ 4.30 in the ¹H NMR spectrum of **6**.

On hydrogenation in presence of palladium/calcium carbonate, paniculatin (**1**) gave the hydrogenated product **2** which was characterised as 1,2,20,21,22,23-hexahydropaniculatin, C₃₀H₄₄O₆, m.p. 212.7 °C. In its ¹H NMR spectrum, the appearance of new signals at δ 2.06 (1H, H-1), 2.61 (s, H-20), 2.80 (1H, d, H-2), 4.14 (s, H-23), 4.18 (s, H-21) and the simultaneous disappearance of the olefinic proton signals at δ 6.39 (1H, d, H-1), 6.62 (1H, m, furan β -H), 6.80 (1H, d, H-2) and 7.53 (1H, m, furan α -H) suggested the hydrogenation of $\Delta^{1,20,22}$ bonds.

On treatment with hydroxylamine hydrochloride in presence of pyridine, the hexahydro product (**2**) gave the ketoxime (**3**). The reaction proceeded more efficiently when the reaction was carried out under microwave irradiation and took only 30 s to complete the reaction and furnish the product in 98% yield. When reacted⁹ with acetyl chloride in presence of acetic anhydride and pyridine, the oxime gave a new heterocyclic compound, characterized as 2-methyloxazolo[4,5-*d*]-1,2,20,21,22,23-hexahydropaniculatin (**4**), C₃₂H₄₅NO₆ (gummy). The reaction was more effective (96%) and took only 60 s to complete when it was carried out in a Prolabo microwave

reactor under solvent-free conditions. In its ^1H NMR spectrum a peak observed at δ 2.60 (3H, s), which could be assigned to $-\text{N}=\text{C}-\text{CH}_3$ in the five membered ring.

On mild hydrolysis methanolic KOH, **4** gave the corresponding diol (**5**), $\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{41}\text{NO}_4$ (gummy), characterized as the corresponding 2-methyloxazolodihydroxyhexahydropaniculatin. Its IR spectrum recorded the hydroxyl band at 3429 cm^{-1} .

On hydrogenation in presence of palladium/calcium

carbonate at room temperature as in the case of **1**, the diol (**6**) gave the corresponding hydrogenated product **7**, $\text{C}_{29}\text{H}_{40}\text{O}_4$, m.p. $95.2\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ which was characterized as $6\alpha,7\alpha$ -dihydroxy-1,2,20,21,22,23-hexahydropaniculatin. In a similar reaction sequence, compound **7** gave the oxime (**8**), which on treatment with acetic anhydride-acetyl chloride gave the new heterocycle (**5**). The reaction also proceeded more efficiently when it was carried out under microwave irradiation and took only 60 s to complete to

Reagents : (i) $\text{H}_2/\text{PdCaCO}_3$; (ii) $\text{NH}_2\text{OH}\cdot\text{HCl}/\text{Py}$; (iii) $\text{CH}_3\text{COCl}/\text{Ac}_2\text{O}/\text{Py}$; (iv) $\text{KOH}/\text{MeOH}, \Delta$; (v) Aq. NaIO_4

Reaction Scheme

furnish the compound **5**, characterized as 2-methyloxazolo-[4,5-*d*]-6 α ,7 α -dihydroxy-1,2,20,21,22,23-hexahydropaniculatin, in 97% yield. In its ^1H NMR spectrum, the characteristic peak for $-\text{N}=\text{C}-\text{CH}_3$ was observed at δ 2.60 (3H, s), as in the case of compound **4**.

On the other hand, the treatment of the compound **6** with aqueous NaIO_4 gave the corresponding dialdehyde (**9**)¹⁰, $\text{C}_{26}\text{H}_{32}\text{O}_4$, m.p. 138.5 °C indicating that the two hydroxyl groups are vicinal. In its ^1H NMR spectrum, peak is observed at δ 9.39 and 9.61 for two CHO groups. The reaction was more effective and took only 35 s to complete when it was carried out in a Prolabo microwave reactor under solvent-free conditions.

The compound **1**, **4**, **5**, **6** and **9** exhibited antifungal activity¹⁰ against the fungi *Rhizoctonia solani* and *Drechslera oryzae* and insecticidal activity against *Helopeltis theivora*.

Conclusion :

In conclusion, our results demonstrated a new, simple and efficient synthesis of one type of novel heterocyclic compounds and a dialdehyde derivative of biological significance. Moreover, the results also demonstrated the advantage of using microwave-assisted reactions in a solvent-free condition.

Experimental

Melting points were determined in open capillaries on a Mettler air heated (Model FP 62) apparatus and are uncorrected. Optical rotations were taken on an optical activity polarimeter (Model AA1000). UV spectra were recorded in MeOH on a Hitachi 320 and Jasco UV-Vis 7800 spectrophotometers, IR, on a Perkin-Elmer system 2000 FT IR spectrometer (ν_{max} in cm^{-1}) and NMR spectra on a Varian EM-360 L NMR spectrometer using TMS as internal standard (chemical shifts in δ , ppm). Mass spectra were recorded on a LC-MS, Bruker (Model esquire 3000) mass spectrometer. Thin layer chromatography (TLC) and preparative TLC were performed on silica gel G (E. Merck) and column chromatography on silica gel (BDH) of 60–120 mesh.

Isolation of compound 1 ($\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{38}\text{H}_6$) : The dry fruits of *Chisocheton paniculatus* were finely ground and extracted with petroleum ether (60–80 °C) in a soxhlet apparatus. The extract on concentration under reduced pressure gave a light yellow material. These materials were washed several times with petroleum ether, followed by ethanol. After careful chromatography with petroleum

ether extract, compound **1** was isolated and recrystallized from methanol, m.p. 191.9 °C. UV : 220 nm (ϵ 10000); IR (ν_{max} cm^{-1}) 1742 (C=O, acetates), 1669 (C=O, cyclohexanone), 1503, 872 (β -substituted furan); ^1H NMR (δ ppm) 7.14 (1H, d, *J* 10 Hz, H-1), 5.93 (1H, d, *J* 10 Hz, H-2); five quaternary methyl groups 1.13 (3H, s, CH_3), 1.26 (3H, s, CH_3), 1.18 (6H, s, 2 CH_3) and 0.81 (3H, s, CH_3), 2.00 and 2.04 (6H, s, 2Ac), 5.47 (1H, H-6), 5.42 (1H, H-7), 5.40 (1H, H-15), 6.28 (1H, m, furan β -H), 7.38 (1H, m, furan α -H); MS : (*m/z*) 494 (M^+), 489 (M^+-CH_3), 434 ($\text{M}^+-\text{CH}_3\text{COOH}$), 374 ($\text{M}^+-2\text{CH}_3\text{COOH}$), 359 [$\text{M}^+(\text{CH}_3\text{COOH} + \text{CH}_3)$].

Preparation of compound 2 : 6 α -Acetoxiazadirone (**1**) (paniculatin) (1 g, 2.0 mmol) in methanol (50 ml) was stirred with palladium/calcium carbonate (0.5 g) under an atmosphere of hydrogen for 6 h in a PAR hydrogenation apparatus. Removal of solvent under reduced pressure gave 1,2,20,21,22,23-hexahydropaniculatin, $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{44}\text{O}_6$, (**2**)⁸, which was crystallized from methanol, m.p. 212.7 °C. IR (ν_{max} cm^{-1}) 1737 (C=O, acetates), 1645 (C=O, cyclohexanone). In the ^1H NMR spectrum, the appearance of new peaks at (δ ppm) 2.06 (H-1), 2.80 (H-2), 2.61 (H-20), 2.06 (H-22), 4.18 (H-21), 4.14 (H-23) suggest the saturated carbon and disappearance of unsaturated carbon protons peak at δ 6.39, 6.62, 6.80 and 7.53; MS : (*m/z*) 500 (M^+).

Preparation of oxime 3 : Hexahydropaniculatin (**2**) (0.8 g, 1.6 mmol), hydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.5 g, 7.1 mmol), 5 ml of ethanol and 0.5 ml of pyridine were treated under microwave irradiation for 30 s. The ethanol was removed by distillation. Water (5 ml) was added to the cooled residue, cooled in an ice bath and stirred until the oxime crystallized. The solid oxime, $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{45}\text{O}_6$, (**3**)⁸ was filtered, washed with a little water, dried and recrystallized from ethanol, m.p. 116.8 °C. IR (ν_{max} cm^{-1}) 3427 (=N-OH); ^1H NMR (δ ppm) 9.30 (1H, s, =N-OH).

Preparation of heterocyclic compound 4 : Oxime (**3**) (0.6 g, 1.17 mmol) was dissolved in pyridine (0.1 g, 1.17 mmol) and acetic anhydride (0.5 ml). To this solution, a mixture of acetyl chloride (0.31 g, 4 mmol) and acetic anhydride (0.5 ml) was added slowly with stirring at 0 °C. The mixture was then treated under microwave irradiation for 60 s and poured into crushed ice (20 g) and extracted with dichloromethane (30 ml). The organic extract was washed with water and dried (anhydrous Na_2SO_4) and concentrated by distillation. The m.p. could not be obtained since the compound⁸ was gummy. IR (ν_{max} cm^{-1}) 1741 (C=O, acetates), 1669 (C=O, cyclohexanone); ^1H

NMR (δ ppm) 2.60 (3H, s, $-N=C-CH_3$).

Preparation of 5 : The compound 4 (500 mg, 0.92 mmol) was refluxed in methanolic KOH (5%, 25 ml) for 2 h in a boiling water bath. Usual work up gave the corresponding diol (5). The m.p. could not be obtained, since the compound is gummy. IR (ν_{\max} cm^{-1}) 3429 (hydroxyl); 1H NMR (δ ppm) 2.60 (3H, s, $-N=C-CH_3$).

Preparation of 6 : Paniculatin (1) (500 mg, 1.0 mmol) was refluxed in methanolic KOH (5%, 25 ml) for 2 h in a boiling water bath. Usual work up gave the corresponding diol (6), which was crystallized from methanol, $C_{26}H_{34}O_4$, (6)⁸, m.p. 181.1 °C. IR (ν_{\max} cm^{-1}) 3443 (hydroxyl), 1662 (C=O, cyclohexanone), 1501 and 873 (β -substituted furan); 1H NMR (δ ppm) 3.90 (2H, s, OH), 7.14 (1H, d, J 10 Hz, H-1), 5.93 (1H, d, J 10 Hz, H-2), five quaternary methyl groups 1.13 (3H, s, CH_3), 1.26 (3H, s, CH_3), 1.18 (6H, s, $2CH_3$) and 0.81 (3H, s, CH_3), 4.30 (1H, q, J 2, 12 Hz, H-6), 4.10 (1H, d, J 2 Hz, H-7), 5.69 (1H, m, H-15), 6.39 (1H, m, furan β -H), 7.36 (1H, m, furan α -H); MS : (m/z) 410 (M^+).

Preparation of 7 : The compound 6 (0.3 g, 0.73 mmol) in methanol (40 ml) was stirred with palladium/calcium carbonate (150 mg) under an atmosphere of hydrogen for 6 h in a PAR hydrogenation apparatus. The mixture was filtered. Removal of solvent under reduced pressure gave 1,2,20,21,22,23-hexahydrodiol, which was crystallized from methanol, m.p. 95.2 °C. MS : (m/e) 416 (M^+); IR (ν_{\max} cm^{-1}) 1700 (C=O, cyclohexanone), 3458 (hydroxyl). In the 1H NMR spectrum, the appearance of new peaks at (δ ppm) 2.06 (H-1), 2.80 (H-2), 2.61 (H-20), 2.06 (H-22), 4.18 (H-21), 4.14 (H-23) suggest the saturated carbon and disappearance of unsaturated carbon protons peak at δ 6.39, 6.62, 6.80 and 7.53.

Preparation of 8 : The compound 8 was prepared in a similar manner as in the case of 3 from 7 (0.2 g, 0.48 mmol), hydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.2 g, 2.9 mmol), ethanol (5 ml) and pyridine (0.2 ml) and recrystallized from ethanol, m.p. 101.3 °C. IR (ν_{\max} cm^{-1}) 3429 ($=N-OH$); 1H NMR (δ ppm) 9.30 (1H, s, $=N-OH$); MS : (m/z) 431 (M^+).

Preparation of 5 from 8 : Oxime (8) (0.1 g, 0.23 mmol) was dissolved in pyridine (0.02 g, 0.23 mmol) and acetic anhydride (0.5 ml). To this solution a mixture of acetyl chloride (0.4 g, 5 mmol) and acetic anhydride

(1 ml) was added slowly, with stirring at 0 °C. The mixture was then treated under microwave irradiation and poured into crushed ice (20 g) and extracted with dichloromethane (30 ml). The organic extract was washed with water and dried (anhydrous Na_2SO_4) and concentrated by distillation. The m.p. could not be obtained, since the compound was gummy.

Preparation of compound 9 : The dihydroxy compound 6 (0.085 g, 0.207 mmol) was taken in 30 ml ethanol and treated with aqueous $NaIO_4$ (12 ml, 57 mmol) for 35 s under microwave irradiation when the reaction was complete (TLC). This was then diluted with water, extracted with ether (30 ml) and dried. Removal of the solvent gave crude product as a gum (70 mg). On preparative TLC using 5% ethyl acetate in benzene, the crude product yielded pure dialdehyde 9, as a crystalline solid (50 mg), m.p. 138.5 °C. IR (ν_{\max} cm^{-1}) 1669 (C=O); 1H NMR (δ ppm) 9.39 (s, $-CHO$); 9.61 (d, J 10 Hz, $-CHO$); MS : (m/z) 408 (M^+).

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